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New Ideas In Cancer's Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Cut As Hyper Vertu On Super Vertigo

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1 ABSTRACT

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a Vertex-Cut pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperVertex-Cut). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called an Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic

v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; an Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; an Extreme V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; a Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; an Extreme V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the

Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. In this scientific research, new setting is introduced for new SuperHyperNotions, namely, a SuperHyperVertex-Cut and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Two different types of SuperHyperDefinitions are debut for them but the research goes further and the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass based on that are well-defined and well-reviewed. The literature review is implemented in the whole of this research. For shining the elegancy and the significancy of this research, the comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are featured. The definitions are followed by the examples and the instances thus the clarifications are driven with different tools. The applications are figured out to make sense about the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. The “Cancer’s Recognition” are the under research to figure out the challenges make sense about ongoing and upcoming research. The special case is up. The cells are viewed in the deemed ways. There are different types of them. Some of them are individuals and some of them are well-modeled by the group of cells. These types are all officially called “SuperHyperVertex” but the relations amid them all officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. The frameworks “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” are chosen and elected to research about “Cancer’s Recognition”. Thus these complex and dense SuperHyperModels open up some avenues to research on theoretical segments and “Cancer’s Recognition”. Some avenues are posed to pursue this research. It’s also officially collected in the form of some questions and some problems. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Then δ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut is a maximal of SuperHyperVertices with a maximum cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the (Neutrosophic) cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$: there are $|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperDefensive; a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut is a maximal Neutrosophic of SuperHyperVertices with maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$ there are: $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive. It’s useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of a SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Since there’s more ways to get type-results to make a SuperHyperVertex-Cut more understandable. For the sake of having Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, there’s a need to “redefine” the notion of a “SuperHyperVertex-Cut”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there’s the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a SuperHyperVertex-Cut. It’s redefined a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut if the mentioned Table holds, concerning, “The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with the key points, “The Values of The Vertices & The Number of Position in Alphabet”, “The Values of The SuperVertices&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The Edges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The HyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The SuperHyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Endpoints”. To get structural examples and instances, I’m

going to introduce the next SuperHyperClass of SuperHyperGraph based on a SuperHyperVertex-Cut . It's the main. It'll be disciplinary to have the foundation of previous definition in the kind of SuperHyperClass. If there's a need to have all SuperHyperVertex-Cut until the SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then it's officially called a "SuperHyperVertex-Cut" but otherwise, it isn't a SuperHyperVertex-Cut . There are some instances about the clarifications for the main definition titled a "SuperHyperVertex-Cut " . These two examples get more scrutiny and discernment since there are characterized in the disciplinary ways of the SuperHyperClass based on a SuperHyperVertex-Cut . For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut" and a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut " . The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's redefined "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" if the intended Table holds. And a SuperHyperVertex-Cut are redefined to a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut" if the intended Table holds. It's useful to define "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut more understandable. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses if the intended Table holds. Thus SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are "Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite", and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel" if the intended Table holds. A SuperHyperGraph has a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut" where it's the strongest [the maximum Neutrosophic value from all the SuperHyperVertex-Cut amid the maximum value amid all SuperHyperVertices from a SuperHyperVertex-Cut .] SuperHyperVertex-Cut . A graph is a SuperHyperUniform if it's a SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows. It's SuperHyperPath if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; it's SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperStar it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperBipartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's SuperHyperMultiPartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's a SuperHyperWheel if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. The SuperHyperModel proposes the specific designs and the specific architectures. The SuperHyperModel is officially called "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". In this SuperHyperModel, The "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperVertices" and the common and intended properties between "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperEdges". Sometimes, it's useful to have some degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy, and neutrality to have more precise SuperHyperModel which in this case the SuperHyperModel is called "Neutrosophic". In the future research, the foundation will be based on the "Cancer's Recognition" and the results and the definitions will be introduced in redeemed ways. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is

identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut or the strongest SuperHyperVertex-Cut in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. For the longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut, called SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and the strongest SuperHyperVertex-Cut, called Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperVertex-Cut. There isn't any formation of any SuperHyperVertex-Cut but literarily, it's the deformation of any SuperHyperVertex-Cut. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form. A basic familiarity with Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut theory, SuperHyperGraphs, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs theory are proposed.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are some ideas in the featured frameworks of motivations. I try to bring the motivations in the narrative ways. Some cells have been faced with some attacks from the situation which is caused by the cancer's attacks. In this case, there are some embedded analysis on the ongoing situations which in that, the cells could be labelled as some groups and some groups or individuals have excessive labels which all are raised from the behaviors to overcome the cancer's attacks. In the embedded situations, the individuals of cells and the groups of cells could be considered as "new groups". Thus it motivates us to find the proper SuperHyperModels for getting more proper analysis on this messy story. I've found the SuperHyperModels which are officially called "SuperHyperGraphs" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". In this SuperHyperModel, the cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperVertices" and the relations between the individuals of cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperEdges". Thus it's another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on the "Cancer's Recognition". Sometimes, the situations get worst. The situation is passed from the certainty and precise style. Thus it's the beyond them. There are three descriptions, namely, the degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality, for any object based on vague forms, namely, incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The latter model could be considered on the previous SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperGraph but it's officially called "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". The cancer is the disease but the model is going to figure out what's going on this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The recognition of the cancer could help to find some treatments for

this disease. The SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognition” and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the forms of alliances’ styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called “ SuperHyperVertex-Cut” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it’s called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn’t be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it’s said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what’s happened and what’s done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they’ve got the names, and some general models. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the optimal SuperHyperVertex-Cut or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath s have only two SuperHyperEdges but it’s not enough since it’s essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperVertex-Cut. There isn’t any formation of any SuperHyperVertex-Cut but literarily, it’s the deformation of any SuperHyperVertex-Cut. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn’t form.

Question 2.1. *How to define the SuperHyperNotions and to do research on them to find the “ amount of SuperHyperVertex-Cut” of either individual of cells or the groups of cells based on the fixed cell or the fixed group of cells, extensively, the “amount of SuperHyperVertex-Cut” based on the fixed groups of cells or the fixed groups of group of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for the “Cancer’s Recognition” in terms of these messy and dense SuperHyperModels where embedded notions are illustrated?*

It’s motivation to find notions to use in this dense model is titled “SuperHyperGraphs”. Thus it motivates us to define different types of “ SuperHyperVertex-Cut” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut” on “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. Then the research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and to find some connections amid this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to get some instances and examples to make clarifications about the framework of this research. The general results and some results about some connections are some avenues to make key point of this research, “Cancer’s Recognition”, more understandable and more clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. In the beginning, I introduce basic definitions to clarify about preliminaries. In the subsection “Preliminaries”, initial definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are deeply-introduced and in-depth-discussed. The elementary concepts are clarified and illustrated completely and sometimes review literature are applied to make sense about what’s going to figure out about the upcoming sections. The main definitions and their clarifications alongside some results about new notions, SuperHyperVertex-Cut and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, are figured out in sections “

SuperHyperVertex-Cut” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut”. In the sense of tackling on getting results and in Vertex-Cut to make sense about continuing the research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, corresponded SuperHyperClasses are figured out to debut what’s done in this section, titled “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. As going back to origin of the notions, there are some smart steps toward the common notions to extend the new notions in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in the sections “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. The starter research about the general SuperHyperRelations and as concluding and closing section of theoretical research are contained in the section “General Results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and they are well-known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions as elicited and discussed in the sections, “General Results”, “ SuperHyperVertex-Cut”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what’s done about the SuperHyperNotions to make sense about excellency of this research and going to figure out the word “best” as the description and adjective for this research as presented in section, “ SuperHyperVertex-Cut”. The keyword of this research debut in the section “Applications in Cancer’s Recognition” with two cases and subsections “Case 1: The Initial Steps Toward SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: The Increasing Steps Toward SuperHyperMultipartite as SuperHyperModel”. In the section, “Open Problems”, there are some scrutiny and discernment on what’s done and what’s happened in this research in the terms of “questions” and “problems” to make sense to figure out this research in featured style. The advantages and the limitations of this research alongside about what’s done in this research to make sense and to get sense about what’s figured out are included in the section, “Conclusion and Closing Remarks”.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [133]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [133]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [133]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [133]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [133]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [133]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (**Ref. [133]**,Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (**Ref. [133]**,Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to **Ref. [133]**.

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [133]**,Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Vertex-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a

falsity-membership function of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref.** [133], Definition 2.2, p.2).

Let X be a Vertex-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (**Ref.** [133], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T_{V'}^l(E_{i'}), T_{V'}^i(E_{i'}),$ and $T_{V'}^f(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T_{V'}^l(E_{i'}), I_{V'}^l(E_{i'}), F_{V'}^l(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.6 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [133], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG).

Definition 3.7 (t-norm). (Ref. [133], Definition 2.7, p.3).

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$:

- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$;
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$;
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$;
- (iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$.

Definition 3.8. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

and $F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$

Definition 3.9. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.10. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.11 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [133], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;

(vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.12. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Definition 3.14. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;

- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 464
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that 465
 $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$. 466

Definition 3.15. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 467

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items. 468

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**; 469
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's V_i , $|V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**; 470
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**; 471
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| \geq 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** . 472
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Definition 3.16 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 474

(Ref. [133], Definition 5.3, p.7). 475

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have 476

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$; 477
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$; 478
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$; 479
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$. 480

Definition 3.17 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [133], Definition 5.4, p.7). 481
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Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 483
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- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 485
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- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 488
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- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 491
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- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

Definition 3.18. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria** holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria** holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

$$\text{and } |E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria** holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria** holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

$$\text{and } |V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Definition 3.19. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperVertex-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut;

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum

- Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 531-534
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 535-544
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; 545-555
- (v) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 556-563
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 564-571
- (vii) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 572-580

Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
Extreme coefficient;

- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's
either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic
re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and
Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial
contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the
maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a
Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that
they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power
is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Definition 3.20. ((Extreme/Neutrosophic) δ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then

- (i) an δ -**SuperHyperVertex-Cut** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic
SuperHyperVertex-Cut such that either of the following expressions hold for the
Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta;$$

$$|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta.$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperOffensive**. And the
Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperDefensive**;

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut** is a Neutrosophic kind of
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut such that either of the following
Neutrosophic expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of
SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta;$$

$$|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta.$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive**.
And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic
 δ -SuperHyperDefensive**.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, there's a need to
"redefine" the notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". The SuperHyperVertices
and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets.
In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.21. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's
more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more
understandable.

Definition 3.22. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2)
holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar,
SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.22)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut more Neutrosophicly understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.23. Assume a SuperHyperVertex-Cut. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if the Table (3) holds.

4 Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 4.1. (Neutrosophic event).

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Any Neutrosophic k -subset of A of V is called **Neutrosophic k -event** and if $k = 2$, then Neutrosophic subset of A of V is called **Neutrosophic event**. The following expression is called **Neutrosophic probability** of A .

$$E(A) = \sum_{a \in A} E(a). \quad (4.1)$$

Definition 4.2. (Neutrosophic Independent).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. s Neutrosophic k -events A_i , $i \in I$ is called **Neutrosophic s -independent** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic s -independent criteria**

$$E(\cap_{i \in I} A_i) = \prod_{i \in I} P(A_i).$$

And if $s = 2$, then Neutrosophic k -events of A and B is called **Neutrosophic independent**. The following expression is called **Neutrosophic independent criteria**

$$E(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B). \quad (4.2)$$

Definition 4.3. (Neutrosophic Variable).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Any k -function Vertex-Cut like E is called **Neutrosophic k -Variable**. If $k = 2$, then any 2-function Vertex-Cut like E is called **Neutrosophic Variable**.

The notion of independent on Neutrosophic Variable is likewise.

Definition 4.4. (Neutrosophic Expectation).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. A Neutrosophic k -Variable E has a number is called **Neutrosophic Expectation** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Expectation criteria**

$$Ex(E) = \sum_{\alpha \in V} E(\alpha)P(\alpha).$$

Definition 4.5. (Neutrosophic Crossing).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. A Neutrosophic number is called **Neutrosophic Crossing** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Crossing criteria**

$$Cr(S) = \min\{\text{Number of Crossing in a Plane Embedding of } S\}.$$

Lemma 4.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let m and n propose special Vertex-Cut. Then with $m \geq 4n$,

Proof. Consider a planar embedding G of G with $cr(G)$ crossings. Let S be a Neutrosophic random k -subset of V obtained by choosing each SuperHyperVertex of G Neutrosophic independently with probability Vertex-Cut $p := 4n/m$, and set $H := G[S]$ and $H := G[S]$.

Define random variables X, Y, Z on V as follows: X is the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperVertices, Y the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperEdges, and Z the Neutrosophic number of crossings of H . The trivial bound noted above, when applied to H , yields the inequality $Z \geq cr(H) \geq Y - 3X$. By linearity of Neutrosophic Expectation,

$$E(Z) \geq E(Y) - 3E(X).$$

Now $E(X) = pn$, $E(Y) = p^2m$ (each SuperHyperEdge having some SuperHyperEnds) and $E(Z) = p^4cr(G)$ (each crossing being defined by some SuperHyperVertices). Hence

$$p^4cr(G) \geq p^2m - 3pn.$$

Dividing both sides by p^4 , we have:

$$cr(G) \geq \frac{pm - 3n}{p^3} = \frac{n}{(4n/m)^3} = \frac{1}{64}m^3n^2.$$

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Theorem 4.7. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let l be the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperLines in the plane passing through at least $k + 1$ of these points, where $1 \leq k \leq 2\sqrt{2n}$. Then $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

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Proof. Form a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdge are the segments between conseNeighborive points on the SuperHyperLines which pass through at least $k + 1$ points of P . This Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph has at least kl SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic crossing at most l choose two. Thus either $kl < 4n$, in which case $l < 4n/k \leq 32n^2/k^3$, or $l^2/2 > 1$ choose $2 \geq cr(G) \geq (kl)^3/64n^2$ by the Neutrosophic Crossing Lemma, and again $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

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Theorem 4.8. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let k be the number of pairs of points of P at unit SuperHyperDistance. Then $k < 5n^{4/3}$.

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Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Draw a SuperHyperUnit SuperHyperCircle around each SuperHyperPoint of P . Let n_i be the Neutrosophic number of these SuperHyperCircles passing through exactly i points of P . Then $\sum i = 0^{n-1}n_i = n$ and $k = \frac{1}{2} \sum i = 0^{n-1}in_i$. Now form a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph H with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdges are the SuperHyperArcs between conseNeighborive SuperHyperPoints on the SuperHyperCircles that pass through at least three SuperHyperPoints of P . Then

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$$e(H) = \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} in_i = 2k - n_1 - 2n_2 \geq 2k - 2n.$$

Some SuperHyperPairs of SuperHyperVertices of H might be joined by some parallel SuperHyperEdges. Delete from H one of each SuperHyperPair of parallel SuperHyperEdges, so as to obtain a simple Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G with $e(G) \geq k - n$. Now $cr(G) \leq n(n - 1)$ because G is formed from at most n SuperHyperCircles, and any two SuperHyperCircles cross at most twice. Thus either $e(G) < 4n$, in which case $k < 5n < 5n^{4/3}$, or $n^2 > n(n - 1) \geq cr(G) \geq (k - n)^3/64n^2$ by the Neutrosophic Crossing Lemma, and $k < 4n^{4/3} + n < 5n^{4/3}$.

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Proposition 4.9. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let X be a nonnegative Neutrosophic Variable and t a positive real number. Then

$$P(X \geq t) \leq \frac{E(X)}{t}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} E(X) &= \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V\} \geq \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= \sum \{tP(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} = t \sum \{P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= tP(X \geq t). \end{aligned}$$

Dividing the first and last members by t yields the asserted inequality. $\square$

Corollary 4.10. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let X_n be a nonnegative integer-valued variable in a probability Vertex-Cut $(V_n, E_n), n \geq 1$. If $E(X_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $P(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof.

Theorem 4.11. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most $\lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$.

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ is up. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ and let S be a given SuperHyperSet of $k+1$ SuperHyperVertices of G , where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The probability that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G is $(1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}$, this being the probability that none of the $\binom{k+1}{2}$ pairs of SuperHyperVertices of S is a SuperHyperEdge of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G .

Let A_S denote the event that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G , and let X_S denote the indicator Neutrosophic Variable for this Neutrosophic Event. By equation, we have

$$E(X_S) = P(X_S = 1) = P(A_S) = (1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

Let X be the number of stable SuperHyperSets of cardinality $k+1$ in G . Then

$$X = \sum \{X_S : S \subseteq V, |S| = k+1\}$$

and so, by those,

$$E(X) = \sum \{E(X_S) : S \subseteq V, |S| = k+1\} = \binom{n}{k+1} (1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

We bound the right-hand side by invoking two elementary inequalities:

$$\binom{n}{k+1} \leq \frac{n^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} \text{ and } 1-p \leq e^{-p}.$$

This yields the following upper bound on $E(X)$.

$$E(X) \leq \frac{n^{k+1} e^{-p} (k+1)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{ne^{-pk/2k+1}}{(k+1)!}$$

Suppose now that $k = \lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$. Then $k \geq 2p^{-1} \log n$, so $ne^{-pk/2} \leq 1$. Because k grows at least as fast as the logarithm of n , implies that $E(X) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Because X is integer-valued and nonnegative, we deduce from Corollary that $P(X = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph in $\mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most k . $\square$

Definition 4.12. (Neutrosophic Variance).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. A Neutrosophic k -Variable E has a number is called **Neutrosophic Variance** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Variance criteria**

$$Vx(E) = Ex((X - Ex(X))^2).$$

Theorem 4.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let X be a Neutrosophic Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) \leq \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let X be a Neutrosophic Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) = E((X - Ex(X))^2 \geq t^2) \leq \frac{Ex((X - Ex(X))^2)}{t^2} = \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Corollary 4.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let X_n be a Neutrosophic Variable in a probability Vertex-Cut (V_n, E_n) , $n \geq 1$. If $Ex(X_n) \neq 0$ and $V(X_n) \ll E^2(X_n)$, then

$$E(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Set $X := X_n$ and $t := |Ex(X_n)|$ in Chebyshev's Inequality, and observe that $E(X_n = 0) \leq E(|X_n - Ex(X_n)| \geq |Ex(X_n)|)$ because $|X_n - Ex(X_n)| = |Ex(X_n)|$ when $X_n = 0$. $\square$

Theorem 4.15. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$. For $0 \leq k \leq n$, set $f(k) := (n \text{ choose } k)2^{-(k \text{ choose } 2)}$ and let k^* be the least value of k for which $f(k)$ is less than one. Then almost surely $\alpha(G)$ takes one of the three values $k^* - 2, k^* - 1, k^*$.

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. As in the proof of related Theorem, the result is straightforward. $\square$

Corollary 4.16. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$ and let f and k^* be as defined in previous Theorem. Then either:

- (i). $f(k^*) \ll 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 2$ or $k^* - 1$,
or

(ii). $f(k^* - 1) \gg 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 1$ or k^* . 771

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. 772
Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 773

Definition 4.17. (Neutrosophic Threshold). 774

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider 775
 $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let P be a monotone property of 776
SuperHyperGraphs (one which is preserved when SuperHyperEdges are added). Then a 777
Neutrosophic Threshold for P is a function $f(n)$ such that: 778

(i). if $p \ll f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely does not have P , 779

(ii). if $p \gg f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has P . 780

Definition 4.18. (Neutrosophic Balanced). 781

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider 782
 $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let F be a fixed Neutrosophic 783
SuperHyperGraph. Then there is a threshold function for the property of containing a 784
copy of F as a Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph is called **Neutrosophic Balanced**. 785

Theorem 4.19. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair 786
 $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let F be a nonempty 787
balanced Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph with k SuperHyperVertices and l 788
SuperHyperEdges. Then $n^{-k/l}$ is a threshold function for the property of containing F 789
as a Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph. 790

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. 791
Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 792

Example 4.20. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair 793
 $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items. 794

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic 795
SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically 796
straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but 797
 E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic 798
SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, 799
there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic 800
SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no 801
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the 802
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic 803
SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 804

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}}$$

$$= \{\}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 0z^0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}}$$

$$= \{\}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 0z^0.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic 805
SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically 806
straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges 807
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Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly

Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 4. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \{E_1\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{V_3\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{V_5\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly

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Figure 5. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 6. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 7. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 8. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
 &= \{E_4\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 9. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 844
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}}$$

$$= \{\}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= 0z^0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}}$$

$$= \{\}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= 0z^0.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 847
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}}$$

$$= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^6.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= 6z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}}$$

$$= \{\}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= 0z^0.$$

Figure 10. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 11. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 12. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 13. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{V_5\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 14. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 15. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 5z^2. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{V_5\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = z^5. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 5z^2. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{V_5\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = z^5. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 16. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 17. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 18. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 876
877
878

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 5z^2. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 879
880
881
882

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} \\ = \{\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 19. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{V_1\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^6. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \{E_2\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{10}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 20. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^9 + z^{12}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 4.21. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

Proposition 4.22. Assume a connected non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an

Figure 21. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 22. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in an Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut, minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

Proposition 4.23. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, then the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut is at least the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut in some cases but the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, has the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut.

Proposition 4.24. Assume a simple Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then the Neutrosophic number of type-result-R-Vertex-Cut has, the least Neutrosophic cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for Neutrosophic cardinality, is the Neutrosophic cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_{E'}, c_{E''}, c_{E'''}\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

If there's a Neutrosophic type-result-R-Vertex-Cut with the least Neutrosophic cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for cardinality.

Proposition 4.25. Assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5. \end{aligned}$$

Is a Neutrosophic type-result-Vertex-Cut. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Neutrosophic type-result-Vertex-Cut is the cardinality of

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The SuperHyperSet of the SuperHyperVertices $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ isn't a quasi-R-Vertex-Cut since neither amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges nor amount of SuperHyperVertices where amount refers to the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperVertices(-/SuperHyperEdges) more than one to form any kind of

SuperHyperEdges or any number of SuperHyperEdges. Let us consider the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

This Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the eligibilities to propose property such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality indicates that these Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets couldn't give us the Neutrosophic lower bound in the term of Neutrosophic sharpness. In other words, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices implies at least on-quasi-triangle style is up but sometimes the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is free-quasi-triangle and it doesn't make a contradiction to the supposition on the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Thus the minimum case never happens in the generality of the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. Thus if we assume in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

Is a quasi-R-Vertex-Cut. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a quasi-R-Vertex-Cut is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

Then we've lost some connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs titled free-triangle, on-triangle, and their quasi-types but the SuperHyperStable is only up in this quasi-R-Vertex-Cut. It's the contradiction to that fact on the generality. There are some counterexamples to deny this statement. One of them comes from the setting of the graph titled path and cycle as the counterexamples-classes or reversely direction star as the examples-classes, are well-known classes in that setting and they could be considered as the examples-classes and counterexamples-classes for the tight bound of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

Let $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ in mind. There's no necessity on the SuperHyperEdge since we need at least two SuperHyperVertices to form a SuperHyperEdge. It doesn't withdraw the principles of the main definition since there's no condition to be satisfied but the condition is on the existence of the SuperHyperEdge instead of acting on the SuperHyperVertices. In other words, if there's a SuperHyperEdge, then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet has the necessary condition for the intended definition to be applied. Thus the $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ is withdrawn not by the conditions of the main definition but by the necessity of the pre-condition on the usage of the main definition.

The Neutrosophic structure of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut decorates the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have received any Neutrosophic connections so

as this Neutrosophic style implies different versions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are spotlight. The lower Neutrosophic bound is to have the maximum Neutrosophic groups of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices have perfect Neutrosophic connections inside each of SuperHyperEdges and the outside of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet doesn't matter but regarding the connectedness of the used Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph arising from its Neutrosophic properties taken from the fact that it's simple. If there's no more than one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex in the targeted Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, then there's no Neutrosophic connection. Furthermore, the Neutrosophic existence of one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has no Neutrosophic effect to talk about the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut. Since at least two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices involve to make a title in the Neutrosophic background of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is obvious if it has no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge but at least two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices make the Neutrosophic version of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the Neutrosophic setting of non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, there are at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. It's necessary to mention that the word "Simple" is used as Neutrosophic adjective for the initial Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, induces there's no Neutrosophic appearance of the loop Neutrosophic version of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and this Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is said to be loopless. The Neutrosophic adjective "loop" on the basic Neutrosophic framework engages one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex but it never happens in this Neutrosophic setting. With these Neutrosophic bases, on a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge thus there's at least a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut has the Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus, a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut has the Neutrosophic cardinality at least a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$. This Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet isn't a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut since either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is an obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel thus it never happens since there's no Neutrosophic usage of this Neutrosophic framework and even more there's no Neutrosophic connection inside or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph isn't obvious and as its consequences, there's a Neutrosophic contradiction with the term "Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut" since the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality never happens for this Neutrosophic style of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet and beyond that there's no Neutrosophic connection inside as mentioned in first Neutrosophic case in the forms of drawback for this selected Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Let

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

Comes up. This Neutrosophic case implies having the Neutrosophic style of on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style on the every Neutrosophic elements of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Precisely, the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that some Neutrosophic amount of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style. The Neutrosophic cardinality of the v SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

Is the maximum in comparison to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}.$$

But the lower Neutrosophic bound is up. Thus the minimum Neutrosophic cardinality of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality ends up the Neutrosophic discussion. The

first Neutrosophic term refers to the Neutrosophic setting of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph but this key point is enough since there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClass of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph has no on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style amid some amount of its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. This Neutrosophic setting of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel proposes a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet has only some amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge such that there's no Neutrosophic amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges more than one involving these some amount of these Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. The Neutrosophic cardinality of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet is the maximum and the Neutrosophic case is occurred in the minimum Neutrosophic situation. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Has the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Contains some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct-covers-order-amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges for amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices taken from the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

It means that the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as used Neutrosophic background in the Neutrosophic terms of worst Neutrosophic case and the common theme of the lower Neutrosophic bound occurred in the specific Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs which are Neutrosophic free-quasi-triangle.

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Then every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has at least no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with others in common. Thus those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices have the eligibles to be contained in a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut. Those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are potentially included in a Neutrosophic style-R-Vertex-Cut. Formally, consider

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

Are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z.$$

where the $\sim$ isn't an equivalence relation but only the symmetric relation on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The formal definition is as follows.

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z$$

if and only if Z_i and Z_j are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices and there's only and only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ between the Neutrosophic

SuperHyperVertices Z_i and Z_j . The other definition for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ in the terms of Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut is

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}.$$

This definition coincides with the definition of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut but with slightly differences in the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality amid those Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$\max_z |\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}|_{\text{Neutrosophic cardinality}},$$

and

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

is formalized with mathematical literatures on the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut. Let $Z_i \overset{E}{\sim} Z_j$, be defined as Z_i and Z_j are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus,

$$E = \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \overset{E}{\sim} Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}.$$

Or

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

But with the slightly differences,

Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut =

$$\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid \forall i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z, \exists E_x, Z_i \overset{E_x}{\sim} Z_j\}.$$

Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut =

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Thus $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut where $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is fixed that means $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. for all Neutrosophic intended SuperHyperVertices but in a Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut, $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ could be different and it's not unique. To sum them up, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, then the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut is at least the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut in some cases but the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, has the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut.

The obvious SuperHyperGraph has no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. But the non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel is up. The quasi-SuperHyperModel

addresses some issues about the Neutrosophic optimal SuperHyperObject. It specially delivers some remarks on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges for distinct amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices up to all taken from that Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is either has the maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality or it doesn't have maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality. In a non-obvious SuperHyperModel, there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge containing at least all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Thus it forms a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut where the Neutrosophic completion of the Neutrosophic incidence is up in that. Thus it's, literarily, a Neutrosophic embedded R-Vertex-Cut. The SuperHyperNotions of embedded SuperHyperSet and quasi-SuperHyperSet coincide. In the original setting, these types of SuperHyperSets only don't satisfy on the maximum SuperHyperCardinality. Thus the embedded setting is elected such that those SuperHyperSets have the maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality and they're Neutrosophic SuperHyperOptimal. The less than two distinct types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are included in the minimum Neutrosophic style of the embedded Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut. The interior types of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are deciders. Since the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperNeighbors are only affected by the interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. The common connections, more precise and more formal, the perfect unique connections inside the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet for any distinct types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices pose the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut. Thus Neutrosophic exterior SuperHyperVertices could be used only in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and in Neutrosophic SuperHyperRelation with the interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in that Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. In the embedded Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut, there's the usage of exterior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices since they've more connections inside more than outside. Thus the title "exterior" is more relevant than the title "interior". One Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has no connection, inside. Thus, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices with one SuperHyperElement has been ignored in the exploring to lead on the optimal case implying the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut. The Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut with the exclusion of the exclusion of all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and with other terms, the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut with the inclusion of all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, is a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut. To sum them up, in a connected non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in an Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut, minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

The main definition of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut has two titles. a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut and its corresponded quasi-maximum Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperCardinality are two titles in the terms of quasi-R-styles. For any Neutrosophic number, there's a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut with that quasi-maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality in the terms of the embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If there's an embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, then the Neutrosophic quasi-SuperHyperNotions lead us to take the collection of all the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cuts for all Neutrosophic numbers less than its Neutrosophic corresponded maximum number. The essence of the Neutrosophic

Vertex-Cut ends up but this essence starts up in the terms of the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut, again and more in the operations of collecting all the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cuts acted on the all possible used formations of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph to achieve one Neutrosophic number. This Neutrosophic number is considered as the equivalence class for all corresponded quasi-R-Vertex-Cuts. Let $z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}$, $S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}$ and $G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}}$ be a Neutrosophic number, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet and a Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut. Then

$$\begin{aligned} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

As its consequences, the formal definition of the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut is re-formalized and redefined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more precise perceptions, the follow-up expressions propose another formal technical definition for the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

In more concise and more convenient ways, the modified definition for the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut poses the upcoming expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To translate the statement to this mathematical literature, the formulae will be revised.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

And then,

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\ & \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ & |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ & = \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more visions in the closer look-up, there's an overall overlook.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ & \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ & S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}}, \\ & |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ & = \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\ & \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ & \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ & S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}}, \\ & |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ & = z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ & |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ & = \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\ & \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ & |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ & = \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\ & = \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\ & \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ & |S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ & = \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, the extension of these types of approaches is up. Since the new term, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood”, could be redefined as the collection of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that any amount of its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are incident to a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. It's, literarily, another name for “Neutrosophic Quasi-Vertex-Cut” but, precisely, it's the generalization of “Neutrosophic Quasi-Vertex-Cut” since “Neutrosophic Quasi-Vertex-Cut” happens “Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut” in a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and background but “Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood” may not happens “Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut” in a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and preliminarily background since there are some ambiguities about the Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality arise

from it. To get orderly keywords, the terms, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood”, “Neutrosophic Quasi-Vertex-Cut”, and “Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut” are up. 1036

Thus, let $z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}$, $N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}$ and $G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}}$ be a Neutrosophic number, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood and a Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut and the new terms are up. 1038
1039
1040

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

1041

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ &|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

1042

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

1043

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

And with go back to initial structure, 1044

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

To make sense with the precise words in the terms of “R-”, the follow-up illustrations are coming up.

The following Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut.

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \}.$$

The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \}.$$

Is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \}.$$

Is an **Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet with

the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge amid some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by **Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut** is related to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

There's not only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet **includes** only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex. But the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

doesn't have less than two SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet since they've come from at least so far an SuperHyperEdge. Thus the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut **is** up. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{xy\}$$

or

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{zy\}$$

is an Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut **and** it's an Neutrosophic **Vertex-Cut**. Since it's

the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut. There isn't only less than two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is up. The non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

does includes only less than two SuperHyperVertices in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ but it's impossible in the case, they've corresponded to an SuperHyperEdge. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the

“Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets called the

Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut,

is only and only

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling. It's also, not only a Neutrosophic free-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel and a Neutrosophic on-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel but also it's a Neutrosophic stable embedded SuperHyperModel. But all only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut amid those obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut, are

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$.

To sum them up, assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

To sum them up, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Vertex-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $ESHE : E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices r . Consider all Neutrosophic numbers of those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from that Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge excluding excluding more than r distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, exclude to any given Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Consider there's a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut with the least cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for Neutrosophic cardinality. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \setminus \{z\}$ is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge

to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely but it isn't a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut. Since it doesn't have

the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some SuperHyperVertices uniquely. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but it isn't a Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut. Since it **doesn't do** the Neutrosophic procedure such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely [there are at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex outside implying there's, sometimes in the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, titled its Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, to that Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S so as S doesn't do "the Neutrosophic procedure"]. There's only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex **outside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$, in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood. Thus the obvious Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut, V_{ESHE} is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut, V_{ESHE} , **is** a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, V_{ESHE} , **includes** only **all** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices does forms any kind of Neutrosophic pairs are titled Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices V_{ESHE} , is the **maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **such that** there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely. Thus, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Any Neutrosophic R-Vertex-Cut only contains all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices and all exterior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from the unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge where there's any of them has all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors in and there's all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhoods in with no exception minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to some of them not all of them but everything is possible about Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhoods and Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors out.

The SuperHyperNotion, namely, Vertex-Cut, is up. There's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. The following Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut}} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic

SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an **Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet with

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the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. There are not only **two** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet **includes** only **two** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. But the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Doesn't have less than three SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut **is** up. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic

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SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut **and** it's an Neutrosophic **Vertex-Cut**. Since it's **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. There aren't only less than three Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut,

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut, not:

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, not:

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Does includes only less than three SuperHyperVertices in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the

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“Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut”

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amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets called the

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Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut,

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is only and only

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. □

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5 The Neutrosophic Departures on The Theoretical Results Toward Theoretical Motivations

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The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses.

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Proposition 5.1. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then*

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_i\}_{i \neq 1, |E_{NSHG}|}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \sum_{i \neq 1, |E_{NSHG}|} z^{|E_i|}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{V_{E_i}\}_{|E_i|=1}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \sum_{i \neq 1, |E_{NSHG}|, |E_i|=1} z^{|V_i|}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &V_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}, V_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.2. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Proposition 5.3. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \\
 C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &V_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Example (16.5)

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\lfloor \frac{ENSHG}{3} \rfloor}, V_{\lfloor \frac{ENSHG}{3} \rfloor}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 5.4. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

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Proposition 5.5. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.

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Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.7)

Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{CENTER\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{|CENTER|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & CENTER, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & E_2, CENTER
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 25. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.9)

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.6. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Proposition 5.7. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Vertex-Cut} \\
 &= \{ \} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Vertex-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Vertex-Cut} \\
 &= \{ \{ One\ From\ Every\ MATCHING\ SuperHyperVertices \} \}, \\
 &= \{ \} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Vertex-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperVertex-Cut could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.8. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Figure 26. Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Example (16.11)

Proposition 5.9. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM : (V, E). Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{ \} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{ \{ \text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices} \} \}, \\
 &= \{ \} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperVertex-Cut could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 5.10. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

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Proposition 5.11. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Vertex-Cut} \\ &= \{\} \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Vertex-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 0z^0. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Vertex-Cut} \\ &= \{\{One\ From\ Every\ MATCHING\ SuperHyperVertices\}\}, \\ &= \{\} \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Vertex-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 27. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Example (16.13)

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperVertex-Cut could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperVertex-Cut proposes some longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.12. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Corollary 6.7. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel) on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut is its SuperHyperVertex-Cut and reverseely. 1303
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Corollary 6.8. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined. 1307
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Corollary 6.9. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined. 1310
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Corollary 6.10. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined. 1313
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Corollary 6.11. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined. 1317
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Corollary 6.12. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined. 1320
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Corollary 6.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined. 1323
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Proposition 6.14. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then V is 1327
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- (i) : the dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1329
- (ii) : the strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1330
- (iii) : the connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1331
- (iv) : the δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1332
- (v) : the strong δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1333
- (vi) : the connected δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1334

Proposition 6.15. Let $NTG : (V, E, \sigma, \mu)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then $\emptyset$ is 1335
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- (i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1337
- (ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1338
- (iii) : the connected defensive SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1339
- (iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1340
- (v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1341
- (vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1342

Proposition 6.16. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then an independent SuperHyperSet is* 1343
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- (i) : *the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1345
- (ii) : *the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1346
- (iii) : *the connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1347
- (iv) : *the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1348
- (v) : *the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1349
- (vi) : *the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut.* 1350

Proposition 6.17. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperVertex-Cut/SuperHyperPath. Then V is a maximal* 1351
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- (i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1354
- (ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1355
- (iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1356
- (iv) : *$\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1357
- (v) : *strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1358
- (vi) : *connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1359

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1360

Proposition 6.18. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperWheel. Then V is a maximal* 1361
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- (i) : *dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1363
- (ii) : *strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1364
- (iii) : *connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1365
- (iv) : *$\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1366
- (v) : *strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1367
- (vi) : *connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1368

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1369

Proposition 6.19. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperVertex-Cut/SuperHyperPath. Then the number of* 1370
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- (i) : *the SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1373
- (ii) : *the SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1374
- (iii) : *the connected SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1375
- (iv) : *the $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1376
- (v) : *the strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut;* 1377

(vi) : the connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1378

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1379
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Proposition 6.20. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperWheel. Then the number of 1381
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(i) : the dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1383

(ii) : the dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1384

(iii) : the dual connected SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1385

(iv) : the dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1386

(v) : the strong dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1387

(vi) : the connected dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1388

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1389
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Proposition 6.21. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices is a 1391
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(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1396

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1397

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1398

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1399

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1400

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1401

Proposition 6.22. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices in the biggest SuperHyperPart is a 1402
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(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1408

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1409

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1410

(iv) : δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1411

(v) : strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1412

(vi) : connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1413

Proposition 6.23. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then Then the number of

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1418

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1419

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1420

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1421

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1422

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1423

is one and it's only S , a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices. Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1424
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Proposition 6.24. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The number of connected component is $|V - S|$ if there's a SuperHyperSet which is a dual

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1430

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1431

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1432

(iv) : SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1433

(v) : strong 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1434

(vi) : connected 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1435

Proposition 6.25. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then the number is at most $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ and the Neutrosophic number is at most $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG)$. 1436
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Proposition 6.26. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E)) \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of dual

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1441

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1442

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1443

(iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1444

(v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1445

(vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1446

Proposition 6.27. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is $\emptyset$. The number is 0 and the Neutrosophic number is 0, for an independent SuperHyperSet in the setting of dual

- (i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1450
- (ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1451
- (iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1452
- (iv) : *0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1453
- (v) : *strong 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1454
- (vi) : *connected 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*. 1455

Proposition 6.28. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. Then there's no independent SuperHyperSet.* 1456
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Proposition 6.29. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperVertex-Cut/SuperHyperPath/SuperHyperWheel. The number is $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG : (V, E))$, in the setting of a dual* 1458
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- (i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1462
- (ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1463
- (iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1464
- (iv) : *$\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1465
- (v) : *strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1466
- (vi) : *connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*. 1467

Proposition 6.30. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStar/complete SuperHyperBipartite/complete SuperHyperMultiPartite. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \sum_{t > \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2}} \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of a dual* 1468
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- (i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1472
- (ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1473
- (iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1474
- (iv) : *$(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1475
- (v) : *strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1476
- (vi) : *connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*. 1477

Proposition 6.31. *Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a SuperHyperFamily of the $ESHGs : (V, E)$ Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs which are from one-type SuperHyperClass which the result is obtained for the individuals. Then the results also hold for the SuperHyperFamily $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ of these specific SuperHyperClasses of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs.* 1478
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Proposition 6.32. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then $\forall v \in V \setminus S, \exists x \in S$ such that* 1483
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- (i) $v \in N_s(x)$; 1486

(ii) $vx \in E$. 1487

Proposition 6.33. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then* 1488
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(i) S is SuperHyperVertex-Cut set; 1490

(ii) there's $S \subseteq S'$ such that $|S'|$ is SuperHyperChromatic number. 1491

Proposition 6.34. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then* 1492
1493

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O}$; 1494

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n$. 1495

Proposition 6.35. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is connected. Then* 1496
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(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O} - 1$; 1498

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n - \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(x)$. 1499

Proposition 6.36. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperPath. Then* 1500

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1501
1502

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1503

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1504

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only a dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1505
1506

Proposition 6.37. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperPath. Then* 1507

(i) the set $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1508

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1509
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(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1511

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1512
1513

Proposition 6.38. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Then* 1514

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1515
1516

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1517
1518

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sigma(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sigma(s)\}$; 1519

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1520
1521

Proposition 6.39. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Then* 1522

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1523
1524
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1525
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1526
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1527
1528

Proposition 6.40. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperStar. Then 1529

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c\}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1530
- (ii) $\Gamma = 1$; 1531
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(c)$; 1532
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1533

Proposition 6.41. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperWheel. Then 1534

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1535
1536
- (ii) $\Gamma = |\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}|$; 1537
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)$; 1538
- (iv) the SuperHyperSet $\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1539
1540

Proposition 6.42. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperComplete. Then 1541

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1542
1543
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$; 1544
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$; 1545
- (iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is only a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1546
1547

Proposition 6.43. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperComplete. Then 1548

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1549
1550
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$; 1551
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$; 1552
- (iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1553
1554

Proposition 6.44. Let $NSHF : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStars with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1555
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- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1557
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- (ii) $\Gamma = m$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1559
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^3 \sigma_j(c_i)$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1560
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1561
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Proposition 6.45. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be an m -SuperHyperFamily of odd SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1563
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- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1566
1567
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1568
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1569
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ are only a dual maximal SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1570
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Proposition 6.46. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of even SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1572
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- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1575
1576
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1577
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1578
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ are only dual maximal SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1579
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Proposition 6.47. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1581
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- (i) if $s \geq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then S is an s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1583
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- (ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1586
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Proposition 6.48. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1589
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- (i) if $s \geq t + 2$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then S is an s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1591
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- (ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1594
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Proposition 6.49. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph$. Then following statements hold; 1597
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- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1600
1601
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1602
1603
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$; 1604
1605
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$. 1606
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Proposition 6.50. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph$. Then following statements hold; 1608
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- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1611
1612
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1613
1614
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$; 1615
1616
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$. 1617
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Proposition 6.51. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph$ which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1619
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- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1622
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- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1624
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- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1626
1627
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1628
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Proposition 6.52. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph$ which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1630
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- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1633
1634
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1635
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- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1637
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(iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Proposition 6.53. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V]$ -SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Then following statements hold;

- (i) $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;
- (iii) $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Proposition 6.54. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V]$ -SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Then following statements hold;

- (i) if $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

7 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it's called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done.

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels.

8 Case 1: The Initial Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. By using the Neutrosophic Figure (29) and the Table (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is obtained. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (29), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut

9 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. By using the Neutrosophic Figure (30) and the Table (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (30), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed.

The SuperHyperVertex-Cut and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 10.1. *Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?*

Question 10.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperVertex-Cut and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut?*

Question 10.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

Question 10.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperVertex-Cut and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut?*

Problem 10.5. *The SuperHyperVertex-Cut and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperVertex-Cut, are there else?*

Problem 10.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

Problem 10.7. *What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, concluding remarks and closing remarks are represented. The drawbacks of this research are illustrated. Some benefits and some advantages of this research are highlighted.

This research uses some approaches to make Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs more understandable. In this endeavor, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the SuperHyperVertex-Cut. For that sake in the second definition, the main definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new definition for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, finds the convenient background to implement some results based on that. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the cases of this research on the modeling of the regions where are under the attacks of the cancer to recognize this disease as it’s mentioned on the title “Cancer’s Recognitions”. To formalize the instances on the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperVertex-Cut, the new SuperHyperClasses and SuperHyperClasses, are introduced. Some general results are gathered in the section on the SuperHyperVertex-Cut and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The clarifications, instances and literature reviews have taken the whole way through. In this research, the literature reviews have fulfilled the lines containing the notions and the results. The SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognitions” and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are

formally called “SuperHyperVertex-Cut” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. In the Table (6), benefits and avenues for this

Table 6. An Overlook On This Research And Beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. SuperHyperVertex-Cut	
3. Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. Modeling of Cancer’s Recognitions	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

research are, figured out, pointed out and spoken out.

12 Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 12.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$ and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$ and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality** if it’s either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality.

Definition 12.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it’s either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the

Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1791
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- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality; 1794
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- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 1802
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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; 1812
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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1823
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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality; 1831
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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either
of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either
of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the
Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients
defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high
Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperDuality; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its
Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 12.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic
SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically
straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is
a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge.
Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex,
 V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge
has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 ,
is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic
SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically
straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges
but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic
SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that
there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic

SuperHyperDuality.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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1882

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1883

1884

1885

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1886

1887

1888

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1889

1890

1891

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1892

1893

1894

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1895
1896
1897

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1898
1899
1900

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1901
1902
1903

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1904
1905
1906

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1907
1908
1909

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1910
1911
1912

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1913
1914
1915

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1916
1917
1918

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1919
1920
1921

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (2 \times 1 \times 2) + (2 \times 4 \times 5)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1922
1923
1924

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1925
1926
1927

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (2 \times 2 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1928
1929
1930

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0}^5}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1931
1932
1933

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1934
1935
1936

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1937
1938
1939

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 9 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 9 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 1940
1941

Proposition 12.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then

1942

1943

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

1944

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

1945

1946

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

1947

1948

1949

Example 12.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperDuality.

1950

1951

1952

Proposition 12.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

1953

1954

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{EXTERNAL}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.10. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then*

1978

1979

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
&= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}, \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
& \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
&= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

1980

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

1981

1982

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

1983

1984

1985

1986

1987

1988

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any

1989

1990

1991

solution

1992

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □ 1993

Example 12.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality. 1994
1995
1996
1997
1998
1999

Proposition 12.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then 2000
2001

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
 &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) choose |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| choose 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2002

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2003
2004

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is 2005
2006

straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 12.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} &= \{E^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2^*, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}^*, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z^* &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z^*. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperDuality proposes some longest SuperHyperDuality excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

13 Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 13.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin.

Definition 13.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; 2063-2070
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; 2071-2078
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2079-2088
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; 2089-2099
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; 2100-2107
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic 2108-2112

SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; 2113
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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2116
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- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. 2126
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Example 13.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items. 2137
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- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin. 2139
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus 2149
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the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin. 2156
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2158
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2161
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2164
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2167
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2170
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2173
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2176
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2179
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2182
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2185
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_{i \neq 5,7,8}^{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2188
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2191
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2194
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2197
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2200
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2203
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2206
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2209
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2212
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2215
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2218
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Proposition 13.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{EXTERNAL}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
 straightforward. □

Example 13.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i | E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
 straightforward. □

Example 13.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied.

There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL}^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL}^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 13.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one

SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperJoin} = \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperJoin} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \prod |V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperJoin proposes some longest SuperHyperJoin excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

14 Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 14.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect.

Definition 14.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2341-2348
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect; 2349-2356
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2357-2366
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; 2367-2377
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2378-2385
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic 2386-2390

SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect;

(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 14.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus

the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect. 2434
2435

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2436
2437
2438

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2439
2440
2441

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2442
2443
2444

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2445
2446
2447

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, E_{3i+24}_{i=0}^3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{3i+1}_{i=0}^7\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2448
2449
2450

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2451
2452
2453

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2454
2455
2456

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2457
2458
2459

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2460
2461
2462

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 2z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2463
2464
2465

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2466
2467
2468

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2469
2470
2471

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2472
2473
2474

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2475
2476
2477

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2478
2479
2480

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2481
2482
2483

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2484
2485
2486

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=03}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=05}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2487
2488
2489

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2490
2491
2492

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2493
2494
2495

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2496
2497

Proposition 14.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\ & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ & = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}} \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\ & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ & = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\{\}, \\ &\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ &z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} &P : \\ &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ &\dots, \\ &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be

applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 14.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 & = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have

one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperPerfect proposes some longest SuperHyperPerfect excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

15 Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 15.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal.

Definition 15.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal;

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;
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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal;
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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
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- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a
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Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 15.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2717
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2720
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2723
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2726
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2729
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly 2732
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straightforward. 2734

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2735
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2738
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2741
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2744
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2747
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2750
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2753
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2756
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2759
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2762
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2765
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_6, E_{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (|V| - 1)z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2768
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2771
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2774
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Proposition 15.4. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then* 2776
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2778

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ V_3^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_3, \\ \dots \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath
 $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &\quad \cdot |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} \cdot |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ \frac{E^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1}}{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1} V^{EXTERNAL}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1} \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESH C : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| &= \\ = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. & \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL} ESHG:(V,E)}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{EXTERNAL} ESHG:(V,E)}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}} &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 15.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 15.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperTotal proposes some longest SuperHyperTotal excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

16 Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 16.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected** if2882
- $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j;$ and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E',$ such2883
- that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j;$ 2884
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected** if2885
- $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j;$ $\forall E_i, E_j \in E',$ such2886
- that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j;$ and2887
- $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$ 2888
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected** if2889
- $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V',$ such2890
- that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ 2891
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected** if2892
- $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a;$ $\forall V_i, V_j \in V',$ such that2893
- $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ and2894
- $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$ 2895
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic2896
- e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic2897
- v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected.2898

Definition 16.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperConnected). 2899

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 2900
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- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic2902
- e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic2903
- v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and2904
- $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum2905
- Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality2906
- of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of2907
- Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form2908
- the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;2909
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic2910
- e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic2911
- v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and2912
- $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum2913
- Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic2914
- SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic2915
- SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the2916
- Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected;2917
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either2918
- of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected,2919
- Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic2920
- rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph2921
- $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme2922
- coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality2923
- of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high2924
- Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme2925
- SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and2926
- the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;2927

- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected;

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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

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Example 16.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3004
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3007
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3010
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3013
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3016
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=11}^{19}, V_{22}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically 3019
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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3037
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3040
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3043
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3046
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3049
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses.

Proposition 16.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= \prod |V^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}P : \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}^{EXTERNAL}.\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \\ & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1) \\ & \quad z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ & V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}^z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\ \forall P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| &= \min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|} \\ \text{where } \forall P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, V_b^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_j^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|} (|P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperConnected} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i| E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-SuperHyperConnected} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V^{EXTERNAL}_i, E^*_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperConnected proposes some longest SuperHyperConnected excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

17 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)” with ISO abbreviation “J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res” in volume 1 and issue 1 with pages 06-14. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [3]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

In some articles are titled “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs” in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition” in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs ” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On

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Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [134]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 3230 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs” and published by Ohio: E-publishing: Educational Publisher 1091 West 1st Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United State. This research book covers different

types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [135]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 4117 readers in Scribd. It's titled "Neutrosophic Duality" and published by Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It's smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what's done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1–3]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions in SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions in SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–133]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 3230 and 4117 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [134, 135].

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